

LEXICO-SEMANTIC FEATURES OF THE NAMES OF PEOPLE USED IN MUKIMI'S WORKS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the thematic groups of anthroponyms used in the works of Mukimi, a representative of the Kokand literary environment.

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We know that "names in poetic works have a broader function than in prose – a methodological connotative meaning. They differ from other categories of anthroponyms by a number of features: they are the main name of a person; ancient in appearance; wide range of applications and active; will be the basis for the emergence of other categories of anthroponyms; used productively and repeatedly in literary monuments (monuments of the XV century — R.J.); performs a specific function and meaning in the text".

The analysis of anthroponyms into lexical-semantic groups is important in revealing such features as the literary and social scope and worldview of the creator. We have found that the names of persons used in Mukimi's works — anthroponyms — belong to the following thematic cells:

1) Anthroponyms with the meaning of "creators who met the poet directly": Muhyi, Nodim, Muhayyir, Zavkiy, Furkat, Almai. The poet had literary conversations and correspondence with these artists. In Kokand he headed a literary circle of young artists.

Hasbi hol aylab qilibdur xat, so'rab holin, Muqim

To qiyomat Furqatidan emdi minnatdorman

2) Anthroponyms with the meaning of "representatives of various fields directly acquainted with the poet": Khoja Inom, Mir Aqil, Mir Gafur, Shamirza, Farzinkhan, Farzincha, Karim axun, Musajon, Movlon aka, Khoja Ahror, Qasim dallol, Sayid Qasim, Eshan, Hajim, Tajikhon, Ghoib barber, Asrorqul, Mahdumxon, Abdufattoh, Sheikh Daloyil, Miyon haji, Nasriddin Khoja, Kalonxon, Mulla Ziya, Khoja Sulaymon, Hakim, Mirza Kamol, Ernazarbek, Mahdumjon, Mulla Sa'dulla, Abdulkarim mirza, Makaylikhon, Haji Muji Muhammadkhan, Mirzaboy, Qori Muhiddin, Ahmad Bobo, Botakoro, Ruzimhammad and others.

Many of the anthroponyms mentioned above are mentioned in the poet's jokes and letters. In particular, the names of Makhdumjon, Mulla Sadulla, Abdulkarim Mirza are mentioned in Mukimi's reply to the poet Furkat. It is clear from the content of the letter that these people had a close relationship with the poet:

Bo'lsa xilvat joy Maxdumjon va sizlar bo'lsangiz
Qilsa hasrat ul kishi ham, ham desam asror man

The anthroponym Makaylikhon Makay is also used in the style of Makaylik:

Bir Makaylikxon bilan yuzlashturalmay, ohkim
Bo'ldi hasratlig' ko'ngul ustig'a qonlar, assalom

Literary scholar G. Karimov writes about Makaylikkhan: "Mamajon Makay is originally named Muhammadjonbek, his father's name is Kasimboy. From Makay or Makayiston village near Kokand. He was born in 1871 in this village. It is known that one of the famous singers of his time, Fergana, in general, has repeatedly toured many cities of Turkestan, showing his art. Mukimi dedicated a number of poems to Mamajon Makai and awarded him for his services as an artist.

Ruzimuhammad is the poet's nephew. This name is not used in the poems of the poet. It is mainly found in Mukimi's letters to his nephew.

3) Anthroponyms with the semaphore "the names of contemporaries mentioned in the poet's muvashshahs": Khojakhon (a ghazal with a radif "Chiqti deng"), Fuladkhon-Polatkhan (a ghazal with a radif "Dream"), Tajikhon (a ghazal with a radif "Mirror of Hus"), Abdalkhan (a ghazal with a radif "Not"), Arifkhan (a ghazal with a radif "Boldi gul"), Asgarchon-Askarjon ("What if I didn't see it before"), Nuruddinkhan (a ghazal with a radif "Ahead"), Fayozkhan (a ghazal with a radif "Kelmas hanuz"), Muhsinhon (a ghazal with a radif "Olmasun"), Jamolkhan ("Jumlai Khoqand mavzun qadlarini sarvari"), Nozimkhan (a ghazal with a radif "Bolay") and others (The above anthroponyms are taken from the newly discovered poems of the poet).

There are 75 muvashshah-ghazals in the works of Shior, and the named people form a creative literary circle. In some of the muwashshah-ghazals, the name, which is formed from the collection of letters at the beginning of the verses (the anthroponyms in the muwashshahs of Mukimi are derived from the collection of the first letter of the words at the beginning of the odd verses), is indicated in the ghazal

Nogohon har baytidin bir harf olib Muqim,
O'qi, noming chiqmas ersa nomusulmoning bo'lay.

4) Anthroponyms with the meaning of "classic traditional images": Layli, Majnun, Farhod, Shirin, Yusuf, Zulayho, Vomiq, Uzro and others.

5) Anthroponyms with the meaning of "legendary, mythological images": Ummisibyon (name of the giant), Nurato, Bibi Ubayda, Erhubbi, Makhdumi Azam, Hotam, Qarun.

According to legend, "Ummisib'yan" is the name of a giant, which causes children's diseases. "Ummisib'yan" is an Arabic adjective meaning "mother of children" ("umm" ("mother") and "sib'yan" means "child").

6) Anthroponyms with the semaphore of "head of state": Alexander, Doro, Mahmud, Ayaz (minister), Takhti Suleiman, Tahmatan, Umarchan-Amir, Mallakhon, Abdulazizkhan and others.

7) Anthroponyms with the meaning of "classic creator, painter, who did not meet the poet directly": Navoi, Jami, Khojandi, Fuzuli, Behzod (painter), Moni (painter) and others.

8) Anthroponyms with the meaning of "prophet, religious-mystical name": Yusuf Canaanite, Hizr, Jacob, Christ, Noah, Ali, Devonai Adham and others.

9) Anthroponyms with the meaning of "doctor, philosopher": Luqman (doctor), Platon, (Falotun), Aristotle and others.

10) Anthroponyms with the meaning of "person who met or heard about him during the journey" (such names are mainly taken from the poem "Travelogue"): Khoja Isa, Eshdavlat, Burhan, Khol Sarkor, Haji Zuhur, Hafiz Umar, Qahhar, Ilyas, Mullah Yuldash Akhun and others

In the thematic groups of anthroponyms used in the works of the poet, it indicates that the artist has an active relationship with representatives of different social strata.

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